

***Environmental assessment of an integrated hydrothermal carbonisation-
aqueous phase reforming-gasification plant using biogenic feedstock***

Preferred Presentation Format (please select one): Visual (or oral)

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1. Life cycle assessment
2. Hydrothermal Carbonisation
3. Process integration

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ABSTRACT

To maximize the valorisation of biogenic waste streams, the EU-funded NIAGARA project proposes a new integrated biorefinery design. This new biorefinery design targets to maximise valorisation and circularity of carbon and energy contained in different biogenic feedstocks. The novelty of NIAGARA design is to combine hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC), aqueous phase reforming (APR), and gasification in a single integrated refinery to produce a gaseous biofuel from various [liquid] feedstocks. This is a pioneer work integrating these technologies and optimizing feedstocks from real-world waste streams combined with microalgae grown with recycled carbon.

This paper focuses on the environmental evaluation of the NIAGARA biorefinery integrating the technologies through a life cycle assessment (LCA). The NIAGARA's project goal is to achieve 30% reduced impacts (e.g., greenhouse gas equivalent emissions) compared to conventional (bio)fuels. To assess the novel NIAGARA plant, several concepts from LCA literature will be combined. Specifically, the LCA inventories will be parametrised to reflect appropriately the impacts from different feedstock compositions and varying process conditions. Further, the study will build on energy-optimized scenarios considering the benefits of heat integration. In the use stage, different market applications, such as solid oxide fuel cells and the production of a liquid biofuel will be compared.

This contribution describes in detail the methodology used to perform the environmental assessment including the LCA's goal and scope definition, system boundaries, a description of the relevant flows in the system, and an indication of how parameters are treated in the assessment. Additionally, any preliminary results from the project's assessment are compared to NIAGARA's target and to literature results on alternative pathways (including anaerobic digestion).

This paper informs about the pioneering EU NIAGARA project and its technology, which can further help researchers to design adequate assessment strategies for similar technologies. In the wider context, this research contributes to environmental sustainability and climate change mitigation.

APPLICABLE TOPIC AND SUB-TOPIC NUMBER

Within the Topic 2: *Sustainability, impacts, policies and systems analysis*, we consider the subtopic 2.2 *Environmental impact* with its explicit mention of environmental life cycle assessment (LCA) a very good fit for this work. This paper focuses on the environmental assessment via LCA methodology of the NIAGARA research project, and will highlight limitations related to the assessment process. Other relevant subtopics are 2.4 and 5.2.

INTRODUCTION:

Environmental sustainability, the energy transition and energy security are key policy objectives in the European Union. The EU HORIZON-funded project NIAGARA (Grant Agreement No 101146861, Start Q2 2024) addresses these aspects by promoting research and development of a novel integrated process to harness energy and carbon contained in biogenic waste streams. The process has the potential to achieve low environmental impacts, potentially negative carbon emissions, and a highly circular value chain.

AIM AND APPROACH

The NIAGARA process will integrate hydrothermal carbonisation (HTC), aqueous phase reforming (APR), and gasification to create a gaseous biofuel (see Figure 1). By valorising both energy and carbon contents via suitable final applications, a high degree of circularity and a low environmental footprint can be achieved.

A parametrised LCA is used to measure the impact of an integrated biorefinery. The parametrisation will ensure to represent the variable feedstock (a mix of biowastes and microalgae) and varying process conditions adequately. Heat integration will be considered using energy-optimised scenarios.

Figure 1: NIAGARA process description (Source: <https://niagara-project.eu/technology/>, accessed 5/11/2024)

SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION AND RELEVANCE

The research extends the current literature by adding a novel integrated plant design and its environmental evaluation. As the NIAGARA project also aims at further development of the involved individual technologies, new results on individual technologies are also expected.

Previously studies have focused on different technologies to assess the usage of waste streams, e.g., more conventional approaches such as anaerobic digestion and incineration (Li et al., 2017), and novel approaches such as anaerobic digestion + HTC (Meisel et al., 2019), HTC + anaerobic digestion (Medina-Martos et al., 2020), HTC + APR (Oliveira et al., 2022). Yet, to our knowledge, no work has assessed the specific NIAGARA configuration.

In addition, the parametrized LCA approach will allow to reflect, from the environmental performance perspective, on different feedstock compositions and a different mixing ratio of microalgae and waste streams, as exemplified for instance in (Isola et al., 2018). This approach ensures to provide results that can be extrapolated and compared to other cases.

RESULTS

This contribution focuses on the outlined methodology with the objective to inform the audience about the methods chosen to conduct the assessment. Additionally, the contribution will inform about the NIAGARA project and expected results. By the time of the conference, preliminary results may be available than can be presented in addition.

CONCLUSIONS

The contribution will showcase the environmental performance of a novel integration of technologies to create a biofuel from varying feedstocks and how it can be assessed using parametrisation to consider variability.

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